

GENDER APPROACH IN PSYCHOLOGY, SOCIOLOGY, EDUCATION

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Abstract. *Gender pedagogy is a set of approaches aimed at helping students feel comfortable in an educational institution and cope with the problem of socialization, an important component of which is the self-identification of a person as a woman or a man. The subject of the study of gender pedagogy, along with others, is the problem of correcting the process of gender-role socialization of the younger generation in the era of global socio-economic and cultural transformations.*

Keywords: *gender education, oriental education, pedagogy, psychology, women and gender equality issues.*

In defining the essence of the concept of "gender pedagogy" in Russian and domestic psychological and pedagogical science, two trends are distinguished:

- gender pedagogy is associated with sex education, while in education and training emphasis is placed on taking into account the gender-role characteristics of students. This approach is most common among psychologists and educators who, until the late 1990s, were engaged in the development of problems of sexual and family education;

- gender pedagogy is considered as a branch of knowledge aimed at the formation of an androgynous personality, at comprehensive education of a child without emphasis on gender.

As noted, the main tasks of the committee are the development of recommendations for the implementation of state policy aimed at ensuring gender equality in the country and the active participation of women in state and public work, consideration of gender equality issues and laws on the development of the institution of the family for their compliance with the goals and objectives of the reforms carried out in the country and the norms of international law, and the submission of relevant conclusions.

The committee is also tasked with developing proposals for the implementation into national legislation of generally recognized international norms for the elimination of all forms of discrimination against women's rights, monitoring the implementation in practice of the norms of international documents on gender equality, to which the Republic of Uzbekistan is affiliated and the implementation of the recommendations established therein.

There were also women in Central Asia who possessed knowledge and creative abilities, who left their mark on the literature and poetry of Uzbekistan – Zebbunisa, a descendant of the Baburid dynasty (1639-1706), Jahan-Atyn Uwaisi and Makhlar-ayim Nadira (XIX century), Dilshod-Barno (1800 - 1905), who studied on the works of Hafiz and Navoi, Anbar-ata (1870-1915).

The twentieth century in Uzbekistan was marked by a triumphant surge of bright creativity of a galaxy of talented women – legendary dancers Tamara Khanum and Mukarram Turgunbayeva, ballerina Bernara Karieva and singer Rano Sharipova, academician and prominent archaeologist-scientist Galina Pugachenkova and many other famous figures of culture and art glorified their country.

"On measures to radically improve measures to support women and strengthen the institution of the family" and the installation of at least 50% of women in public and private structures of the country's economy. These issues reflected in this book, the role and importance of women in the modern world, as well as the prospects for the development of the movement for equal rights of women in the Central Asian and Asia-Pacific regions and many other tasks were discussed at this seminar with the participation of Vice President Mr. Shixin Chen and Deputy Prime Minister, Chairman The Women's Committee of Uzbekistan Ms. Tanzila Narbayeva.

In order to eliminate the shortcomings identified during the monitoring and improve the situation of ensuring women's labor rights at the enterprises of the textile industry of the Fergana Valley, the Commissioner for Human Rights has developed appropriate recommendations. [2]

Education in general education schools and other educational institutions is not divided by gender – girls and boys study together.

A lot of work is being done in Uzbekistan on legal education of women both at the central and local levels. Awareness-raising and educational activities are carried out by both State and non-State structures together with international organizations.

Tashkent, Uzbekistan (UzDaily.uz) – On December 28, 2019, a meeting of the Commission on Gender Equality of the Republic of Uzbekistan was held. It was attended by members of the Commission, representatives of ministries and departments, non-governmental non-profit organizations and the media.[1]

The meeting was chaired by the Chairman of the Commission on Gender Equality of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Chairman of the Senate of the Oliy Majlis Tanzila Narbayeva.

An important area of the Commission's activity was the wide promotion and enforcement of the adopted laws. Thus, normative legal acts were brought into line with the laws "On guarantees of equal rights and opportunities for men and women", "On the protection of women from harassment and violence". The Commission, together with a number of reputable international organizations, held international forums, conferences, seminars, and actions under the motto "We are against violence".

It was emphasized that behind each figure given at the meeting, large-scale work carried out in a short time, there are the fates of ordinary women who, thanks to the assistance provided by the Commission, found housing or a permanent place of work, perked up and began to look at life in a new way, realizing that they are not alone and they have someone to rely on.

The term "gender" emphasizes that the biological characteristics of sexuality are not given to a person directly, but are refracted through the prism of individual consciousness and social representations, i.e. they exist in the form of subjective and culturally fixed knowledge about them. Most modern scientists agree that gender is a social construct that is formed in a person during life in the processes of socialization, upbringing and education and can change depending on a number of external factors. In accordance with this, the following components are distinguished in its structure: gender-role (gender) stereotypes, gender roles, gender identity, gender display, gender contract, gender system [3, p. 88].

Gender is the designation of a spectrum of a certain spectrum of characteristics that relate to femininity and masculinity. That is, in fact, this is a list of characteristics that are inherent in representatives of a certain sex. That is why many people confuse this concept with gender and sexual characteristics. But it should be remembered that there are significant differences between these two concepts.

The structure of gender can also be represented as a three – element system:

- cognitive component – human gender identity ("I know I'm a woman/man");
- emotional component – gender identity ("I feel like a woman/man");
- behavioral component – gender roles and behavioral characteristics ("I behave like a woman/man") topic [3, p. 6].

Within the framework of gender pedagogy, the following aspects and processes of the modern education system are analyzed:

- its feminization (a significant predominance of women at low–paid levels of the system - in kindergartens and schools) and the associated decline in the prestige of pedagogical professions in society as a whole;
- improving its content based on the analysis of curricula and textbooks from the point of view of gender equality;
- the style of teaching and interaction of teachers with students, revealing gender stereotypes and sexism – an explicit or implicit demonstration of the superiority of one sex over the other.

Methodological foundations in the research of gender pedagogy are:

- cultural-historical theory of personality development, recognizing the priority of the social over the biological in human mental development (L. S. Vygotsky, A. N. Leontiev, A. R. Luria, etc.);
- postmodern ideas about the constructivist nature of culture, the socio-constructivist nature of human knowledge and experience, about gender and sexuality of a person;
- the ideas of sociologists and psychologists about gender identity as the basic structure of personality at all stages of its development, about the continuity of the process of constructing and reconstructing gender by each individual throughout his life; about the nature of the relationship between the child and society in the process of gender socialization;
- the doctrine of androgyny as a condition for the effective development and self-realization of the individual (S. Bem);
- pedagogical anthropology as a philosophical basis of education (B. M. Bim-Bad) [3, p. 88].

The most well - known works on gender pedagogy are V. Portnoy "Gender pedagogy", N. Y. Erofeeva "Gender pedagogy", "Gender approach in preschool pedagogy: theory and practice" (edited by L. V. Shtyleva), etc.

Gender education is inextricably linked with moral, civil, sexual, as well as with the education of the culture of family relations.

The basis for the formation of gender stereotypes in the younger generation, the foundation for the development of gender roles and the demonstration of gender behavior is the moral education of the individual. It is in it that the value foundations for gender education are laid, not only the abstract concepts of "good" and "bad" are manifested, but also their refraction through the prism of gender ("good/bad for a boy, a man", "good/bad for a girl, a woman").[4]

The school forms many ideas about professional self-determination, life strategy, access to resources and power, based on gender orientation. The development of gender education at school will allow the younger generation to form the idea that gender is not a basis for discrimination on any basis, it enables a woman and a man to enjoy all human rights, helps to overcome "glass

ceilings", assumes a free choice of ways and forms of self-realization by a man or woman, taking into account their individuality.[5]

The tasks of pedagogical support of gender education are:

- psychological education of students, parents and teachers on the entire spectrum of gender issues;
- diagnostics of the formation of the gender component of personal development of students;
- advising students, parents and educators on gender differences and gender relations;
- correctional and training work to develop students' gender identity and gender tolerance, to gain experience in effective gender interaction and overcoming the negative consequences of gender stereotypes.

The following documents are identified as the main conditions for the successful implementation of gender education of the younger generation in the above-mentioned documents:

- 1) integration of the efforts of the family, employees of the education and health systems in the formation of the gender culture of students;
- 2) improvement of the gender culture of teachers and parents.

A special place is given to the creation of opportunities for the observation and implementation of gender roles by students from single-parent families, orphans.

Gender education is also complemented by the education of a culture of family relations, which is aimed at acquiring students' knowledge about family and marriage, family pedigree, fatherhood and motherhood, participation in various activities that contribute to the preparation of students for future family life.

The problems of gender socialization in the scientific literature are analyzed at three levels:

- macrosocial – we are talking about the differentiation of social functions by gender and the corresponding cultural norms.

The description of gender issues at this level involves the disclosure of the specifics of the social status of men and women: typical activities, social statuses, mass representations, etc. For this purpose, research results and knowledge gained in such disciplines as sociology, demography, history, ethnography, ethnology and cultural anthropology are used;

- microsocial, ethnology and cultural anthropology;
- at the level of interpersonal relations, gender problems are generated not only by general social norms and practices, but also by a specific system of joint activities and social attitudes typical of a certain small group. Consideration of gender relations at this level is based mainly on socio-psychological knowledge;

- individual – internalized sexual role is derived from the characteristics of a particular personality, an individual builds his gender role behavior on the basis of conscious or unconscious attitudes, stereotypes, life experience. The study of these plots is based on the ideas of age psychology and personality psychology.

The scientific study of gender problems, including pedagogical ones, has advanced in modern science: fundamental works of a theoretical and applied nature have been written; research is being conducted on the problem of gender socialization; gender and gender are considered as the most important human characteristics; attempts are being made to develop concepts of gender education of modern schoolchildren.[5]

The role of the mother in the upbringing of children. The different behavior of the mother, depending on the sex of the child, attracts attention from the very first weeks of his life. During the first months, mothers are more often in physical contact with their sons, but they talk more with girls. After the sixth month, mothers have increased physical contact with girls. Subsequently, boys are weaned from physical contact earlier than girls.

But, unfortunately, the gender education programs being developed today are often limited to physiological and medical aspects and miss pedagogical ones, do not take into account the richest domestic psychological and pedagogical heritage, which requires urgent study and further rethinking.

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